

GERB-HR-ED01 rsut 1hrCM v1.1

**TOA outgoing shortwave radiation, monthly-mean diurnal cycle
resolving each day into 1-hour means**

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Document Contents

1. Intent of This Document and Point Of Contact.....	2
2. Data Field Description.....	2
3. Data Origin	2
4. Validation and Uncertainty Estimate.....	6
4.1 Absolute accuracy	6
4.2 Radiance to flux uncertainties	6
4.3 Impact of missing data and data filling	6
5. Considerations for Model-Observation Comparisons	11
6. Instrument Overview	11
7. References	12
8. Dataset and Document Revision History	12

1. Intent of This Document and Point Of Contact

1a) This document is intended for users who wish to compare satellite derived observations with climate model output in the context of the CMIP/IPCC historical experiments. Users are not expected to be experts in satellite derived Earth system observational data. This document summarizes essential information needed for comparing this dataset to climate model output. References are provided at the end of this document to provide additional information.

This GERB dataset is provided as part of an activity to increase the usability of GERB satellite observational data for the modelling and model analysis communities.

Whilst this is not produced as part of the standard GERB data processing, the need for a product suitable for routine model evaluation prompted its creation. Therefore, standard GERB data products have been reprocessed and reformatted, utilising additional data sources where necessary, to create a product primarily intended for comparisons with climate model output.

Users of these data should ensure they reference Harries *et al.* (2005) in any presentations or publications.

Dataset File Name (as it appears on the ESGF):

rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200701-200712.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200801-200812.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_200901-200912.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201001-201012.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201101-201112.nc
rsut_1hrCM_GERB-HR-ED01-1-1_BE_gn_201201-201212.nc

1b) Technical point of contact for this dataset:

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2. Data Field Description

CF variable name, CMIP short name, units:	toa_outgoing_shortwave_flux, rsut, W m ⁻²
Spatial resolution:	1° × 1°
Temporal resolution and extent:	1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means), from 200705 to 201212
Coverage:	Area bound by 60°N/S by 60°E/W

3. Data Origin

The Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget (GERB, Harries *et al.* 2005) instruments operate on board the four Meteosat Second Generation (MSG, Schmetz *et al.* 2002) series of geostationary satellites (Meteosat-8 through to 11). The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers that provide observations, approximately every 15 minutes, of the Earth's emitted longwave (~4.0 to 100 μm)

radiation and reflected shortwave (~ 0.32 to $4 \mu\text{m}$) radiation over a geographical region roughly from 60°N to 60°S in latitude and 60°W to 60°E in longitude. Also onboard each of the Meteosat satellites is the Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) which provides observations of the reflected shortwave and emitted longwave radiances in narrow bands over the same nominal region but at a higher spatial resolution. Data from the SEVIRI instruments are used widely by the operational meteorological and research community and are employed in several steps in the GERB product processing (Brindley and Russell, 2018).

The GERB reflected solar radiances are derived from the GERB observations (except for specific cases of filled data – described below) using information on the spectral properties of the scene, viewing geometry and solar illumination. Reflected shortwave radiation (RSW) fluxes are determined from these reflected solar radiances using empirically derived angular distribution models (ADMs). These ADMs have been built up from broadband observations obtained by the CERES instrument on the Tropical Rainfall Measuring Mission (TRMM) with some supplementation with models to fill in missing observational conditions (Loeb *et al.*, 2003). The appropriate ADM is chosen according to the underlying surface type (for GERB Edition 1 data this is a fixed surface type map) along with cloud cover, cloud optical depth and cloud phase which are retrieved from coincident SEVIRI shortwave channel radiances. Spatial information from the SEVIRI instrument is also used to correct for the spatial response of the GERB footprint.

It is important to note that there are two conditions under which the reflected shortwave fluxes are not derived from the instantaneous observed GERB radiances: (1) clear ocean scenes within 25° of the glint angle and (2) twilight conditions defined as the solar zenith angle range 85° to 100° . In both these cases the radiance to flux conversion is not reliable and climatological fluxes are used. For twilight this is fixed model derived from CERES observations (Kato and Loeb 2003), for the clear ocean it is based on the clear ocean GERB fluxes for that location and month adjusted in solar zenith using the TRMM models. In addition, for solar zenith angles between 80° and 85° and over ocean within 15° of the glint angle, the scene identification is extrapolated from a neighbouring time rather than contemporaneously inferred from SEVIRI. Users should note that due to the persistently low solar zenith angle data are not provided for the latitude bands from 55.5° to 59.5° N during November, December and January, and from 55.5° to 59.5° S during May, June and July each year owing to insufficient observational data.

For all of these conditions it is expected that the accuracy at the hourly timescale of the products will be lower. However, the bias will reduce when averaged over hours and should be negligible once averaged over the full diurnal cycle. Further details are provided in Russell, 2018.

The GERB Edition 1 level 2 standard data products released to the scientific community are determined from measurements obtained by the GERB instruments on Meteosat-8 and Meteosat-9. Comprehensive inter-calibration studies using coincident data from these instruments have been undertaken to ensure that the data from these two instruments are aligned to the same radiometric scale and for the RSW user applied corrections are recommended to achieve this. A study performed by Parfitt *et al.* (2016), provided a correction to the GERB-1 RSW products that must be applied to ensure these data are on the same radiometric scale as GERB-2, and also accounts for instrument RSW aging effects. The resulting recommended “user” applied correction is detailed in Russell (2017) and has been applied to the Edition 1 GERB High-Resolution (HR) RSW flux products used to generate the 1hrCM (monthly-mean diurnal cycle resolving each day into 1-hour means) *rsut* products described in this technical note. The GERB HR data products are specifically designed to facilitate spatial and

temporal averaging. They are resolution enhanced snapshots at the SEVIRI acquisition time, every 15 minutes, on a fixed equal viewing angle grid matched to 3×3 SEVIRI pixel grid-boxes.

At present, only data from the GERB instrument onboard Meteosat-9 (GERB-1) have been processed for submission to the obs4MIPs archive covering the period from May 2007 until December 2012. However, during this period, owing to operational constraints of the GERB instrument, data are unavailable for four months of each year (March, April, September, and October) and these months are not present in the record. Observing gaps in the GERB data for the other months also exist, including systematically missing data for the latter half of every February and August due to operational constraints and more randomly distributed observing outages ranging from an hour to a few days which occur through the rest of the record. A method has been devised and implemented to enable those data gaps to be filled, thus producing a set of monthly hourly mean products with reduced uncertainties and increasing the availability of the products for the eight months of each year.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the processing chain employed to generate the 1hrCM *rsut* product from the GERB level 2 HR RSW fluxes. There are five main stages. The first is to take the Edition 1 GERB HR SW flux data with the user corrections applied and generate an albedo using knowledge of the incoming SW flux for each location and time. The albedo is then area weighted to create a 1° by 1° spatial resolution albedo for every 15-minute time interval. These data are then averaged over time to produce an hourly averaged albedo product for each hour of each day. Each hour interval is defined as the time-centred mean at half-past the hour, e.g. 1030 UTC comprises the mean of albedos from 1000 UTC, 1015 UTC, 1030 UTC and 1045 UTC (or from those slots in this window that are available). An hourly average albedo is produced for a 1° by 1° grid cell if there is one or more observation from the four observation times available for that grid cell. The averaged albedos are converted back to RSW flux using the incoming solar flux at the midpoint of the hour and 1° cell. The fourth stage identifies days where there are no observations available for the hour and fills them with broadband RSW fluxes derived from the narrowband SEVIRI data, averaged to the daily hourly scale in the same way as the GERB data and corrected to the GERB observations at the monthly hourly 1° scale¹. Finally, a monthly mean for each hourly time step is calculated encompassing the full data. The number of filled data points (days per monthly hourly average) contributing to each monthly hourly mean are used to estimate the uncertainties associated with the product. This is discussed in more detail in section 4.

Important notes:

1. For an hourly average value to be produced for a 1° by 1° grid cell, at least one observation from the four observation times must exist for that grid cell.
2. Grid cells are considered to be in twilight when their central latitude and longitude have an associated solar zenith angle (SZA) for a 15-minute time in the range $100^\circ > \text{SZA} > 85^\circ$. Their flux is then set to that derived from a fixed twilight model (Kato and Loeb, 2003). Similarly, grid cells with $\text{SZA} > 100^\circ$ are considered night-time points and their SW flux is set to 0.0 W m^{-2} .

¹ Broadband flux estimates derived from SEVIRI as part of the standard GERB processing are referred to as GERBlike data. To make them suitable for filling missing GERB data, they are scaled by the ratio of the monthly hourly 1° by 1° averages for the available GERB and matched GERBlike data. These scaled GERBlike fluxes are used to fill the missing GERB observations at the daily hourly scale before averaging over the month.

Figure 1: Summary of the processing steps employed to produce the GERB SW Flux obs4MIPs monthly hourly mean at $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$.

An example of the GERB monthly hourly mean reflected SW flux at the TOA (*rsut*) product for December 2012, plotted from 00:30 to 22:30, is shown in figure 2. There are many notable features including the contrast between the brighter desert surfaces (e.g. Sahara, Namib, and Kalahari), bright (reflective) clouds over tropical Africa and at the southernmost latitudes, and the darker clear-sky ocean surfaces as well as the diurnal variation due to the changing solar illumination conditions.

Figure 2: Example GERB Edition 1 monthly hourly mean SW flux products (*rsut*) for hourly intervals for June 2008, starting at 00:30 (top left), to 23:30 (bottom right), over the nominal geographical region from 60°N to 60°S by 60°W to 60°E .

4. Validation and Uncertainty Estimate

There are three main sources of error that have been considered which are the absolute accuracy of the GERB radiance measurement, the uncertainties in determining a flux from a radiance, and the impact of missing data and filling on these average fluxes.

4.1 Absolute accuracy

Quoted bias errors for GERB reflected solar radiances are 2.25% for a typical full scale radiance ($240 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ sr}^{-1}$). A detailed description of the absolute accuracy of the GERB reflected solar radiance measurements is discussed in Russell (2017) which considers the impact of uncertainties in the geolocation of the measured radiances and provides cautions with respect to aerosols and thin cloud. Russell (2017) also provides details of the recommended user applied “SW combined correction” which accounts for the reduction in the GERB SW response due to instrument aging effects and unifies the records of the GERB instruments on Meteosat-8 and Meteosat-9. This user applied correction was applied to the GERB SW data used to generate the GERB *rsut* products in addition an adjustment to the GERB SW fluxes from the surface level to 20km level has been made to make them more compatible with model output (see Loeb *et al.* 2002).

4.2 Radiance to flux uncertainties

GERB SW fluxes use the CERES TRMM ADMs for their radiance to flux conversion. Users are referred to the relevant CERES documentation and quality summaries for details concerning the accuracy of the ADMs themselves (see Loeb *et al.* 2003). GERB Edition 1 fluxes do not include an adjustment for the apparent aerosol optical depth and use interpolation of a monthly climatology to determine the wind speed for selection of the appropriate ocean ADM. Thus, errors are expected to be larger in the presence of significant aerosol events. Comparison of co-angular fluxes between GERB and CERES indicates that differences in implementation including scene ID results in a 1% elevation in SW fluxes due to the conversion as applied to the GERB products. The ADMs which are the basis of the radiance to flux conversions are statistical in nature and thus a random error will be associated with the instantaneous flux estimates: for the reflected shortwave the 1SD value of this error is 14 Wm^{-2} . Due to the fixed viewing geometry of the GERB instruments, for a given hour this error only reduces significantly in the monthly average if there is significant scene variability. For persistently clear scenes in particular it will likely remain of the order 10 Wm^{-2} in the monthly hourly average and present as a bias for that location and time. For regions where cloud conditions are variable, or for averages over different times of day the error is expected to reduce by the root of the number of different conditions and/or different view geometries averaged.

4.3 Impact of missing data and data filling

Even for the months not affected by observing operational constraints, there are often days with missing hours. This occurs for a variety of reasons and tends to be relatively random with regards to timing.

There are also systematically missing days data with the GERB observations in the latter half of every February and August due to operational constraints. To assess the impact of such missing data on the quality of the monthly mean diurnal product, all hours with no more than one missing day in the month were used to investigate and quantify the effect of removing days on the calculated RSW

monthly hourly mean at the 1 degree scale. Days randomly distributed through the month were removed with 8 selection realisations used to assess the robustness of the results. The difference in the monthly hour mean at the 1-degree scale due to the data removed was determined both before and after filling the data removed as described in section 3.

Table 4.1 summarizes the resulting distributions of the monthly hourly 1-degree differences in terms of the mean and standard deviation. The values shown are the average over all the test cases in the 10:30 to 15:30 UTC range, which corresponds to the high illumination conditions over the region and thus the largest absolute errors. In all cases no significant overall bias is introduced, but the magnitude of the expected error at the 1-degree scale increases roughly linearly with the number of missing days. For the unfilled data this results in an increase in the standard deviation from just over 3.6 W m⁻² for one missing day to in excess of 15 W m⁻² for twelve missing days. The comparable results for the filled data show a significant reduction in the estimated uncertainties, with a standard deviation of just over 0.7 W m⁻² for twelve missing days which have been subsequently filled. The results in the table are the average over eight different realisations of the chosen missing days and over all months and hours in the 10:30 to 15:30 UTC time range where there is no more than one missing day. The range in the standard deviations contributing to this average can be seen in figure 3 which shows the individual standard deviations for all the realisations and cases in 1030 to 1530 UTC range. Results for the unfilled (top group of lines) and filled (bottom group of lines) are shown. The different colours represent the cases from different months, and the spread of each colour represents the variation in time (hour) and realisation for each month. The solid black lines show the mean standard deviation for the unfilled and filled cases, values of which are shown for a selection of missing days in table 4.1.

	SW flux uncertainty estimate (W m ⁻²)					
Number of missing days	1	3	5	7	9	12
Mean unfilled difference	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.05
Average unfilled standard deviation	3.63	6.41	8.55	10.53	12.77	15.79
Mean filled difference	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Average filled standard deviation	0.17	0.30	0.40	0.49	0.60	0.73

Table 4.1: Summary of the difference between no missing days and up to twelve randomly removed (missing) days in the monthly hourly mean SW 1-degree flux. Results are the average of eight realisations of days removed for all the hours in the 10:30 to 15:30 UTC range in the record where there is no more than one missing day in the month and are shown for both the unfilled and the filled results.

Figure 3: Standard deviation (σ) in the monthly hourly mean SW flux difference at the 1-degree scale as a function of number of randomly chosen missing days of GERB data (N). Different colours represent different months, and the spread of curves of the same colour represents the variation in time (hour) from 1030 to 1530 UTC and realisation of random removal of days. The upper group of curves are the unfilled cases and the lower group of curves are the filled cases. The solid black line represents the mean standard deviation for each set of curves.

To further increase the availability of monthly hourly mean data produced, an investigation into the uncertainties associated with the removal of consecutive days of data from the record was undertaken. Once again, as for the random removal of days, the investigation used only hours in the record where there was no more than one missing day in the month. For these cases, from three to twenty-two consecutive days were removed prior to calculating a monthly hourly mean. Three different scenarios were considered: the removal of consecutive days from the start, middle and end of each month. The resulting differences in the monthly hourly average at the 1-degree scale due to missing data were calculated for the unfilled data and after filling with a scaled broadband product. A summary of the resulting 1-degree differences, for a selection of number of consecutive days removed, are shown in table 4.2 in terms of the mean and average standard deviation of the difference distribution for all cases between 1030 and 1530 UTC. Outside of these times, the errors generally reduce steadily with the reduction in incoming solar illumination, noting that for hours before 04:30 and after 19:30 UTC, when less than 20% of the region is illuminated difference distributions over the illuminated points become quite noisy due to limited number of points included. Once again the results indicate that the removal of a significant number of days from the record does not yield a significant bias in the mean difference, but there is a significant increase in the standard deviation (spatial variability) in excess of 40 W m^{-2} for twenty-two consecutive missing days for the 1030 to 1530 UTC times considered. However, in contrast, the comparable results for the filled data indicate a standard deviation of less than 2 W m^{-2} for 22 days removed and then filled with a scaled broadband product.

	SW flux uncertainty estimate (W m^{-2})					
	3	5	7	12	16	22
Number of systematic missing days	3	5	7	12	16	22
Mean unfilled difference	-0.10	-0.14	-0.12	0.01	-0.02	0.00
Average unfilled standard deviation	7.40	10.45	13.22	20.20	26.50	40.13
Mean filled difference	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03
Average filled standard deviation	0.34	0.49	0.62	0.96	1.27	1.92

Table 4.2: Summary of the difference at the 1-degree scale in the monthly mean SW flux due to up to twenty-two consecutively removed (missing) days in the monthly hourly mean. Results are averaged over three realisations of the location of missing days for all the hours in the record between 1030 and 1530 UTC with no more than one missing day in the month. Average mean and standard deviation of the 1-degree differences are shown for the unfilled and filled cases.

The spread in standard deviation for the 3 different realisations of systematic removal of up to 22 consecutive days in record, for all applicable cases between 1030 to 1530 UTC, is shown in figure 4 for both the unfilled (upper group of curves) and the filled results (lower group of curves). The different colours represent the cases from different months, and the spread of each colour represents the variation over the hours from 1030 to 1530 UTC, and realisations for each month. The solid black lines show the mean standard deviation of the unfilled data (top series of curves) and the corresponding filled data cases (lower series of curves) values of which are shown for a selection of missing days in table 4.2.

Figure 4: Standard deviation (σ) of the 1-degree monthly hourly mean difference in the SW flux as a function of missing days or GERB data (N) within the month. Different colours represent different months, and the spread of curves of the same colour represents the variation with hour from 1030 to 1530 UTC and realisation of the location of missing days. Upper curves show the unfilled results and lower curves the result after filling the removed days. The solid black line represents the mean standard deviation for each set of curves.

Figure 5 provides an overview of the amount of GERB SW hourly observations missing in the monthly mean flux products from 2007 to 2012. Areas shaded grey are where there are more than 22 days of GERB data missing, these regions occur for recurring periods each year owing to instrument operational constraints and too little GERB data are available to produce any products. Additional areas shaded grey are December 2007, May and December 2008 and August 2009 where extended satellite outages result in the unavailability of both GERB observations and the data used to fill missing observations. Where there are fewer than 22 days missing in the month and available data for filling, the figure indicates the number of days missing with zero days coloured white, one to five days missing coloured green and 6 to 22 days missing coloured yellow.

Compared to the original release (v1.0) of these products, hours shown in white in figure 5 indicate those data which have not changed in the latest release. Those hours in green were included in the original release but the filling used in this release will improve the fidelity of the averages over the unfilled averages contained in v1.0. Hours shown in yellow are made available for the first time in this release as they were excluded from v1.0 due to the size of the errors associated with this quantity of the unfilled missing data.

Therefore, this latest release of the GERB *rsut* product not only reduces the uncertainties associated with the data previously released, but also significantly increases the availability of data.

Figure 5: Summary of the periods when GERB-1 Edition 1 data are available to produce the *rsut 1hrCM* products from 2007 to 2012. Data are available for those periods indicated in white (no missing days per monthly hourly mean), green (up to five missing days of GERB data filled) and yellow (up to twenty-two missing days of GERB data filled). Shown in grey are those periods in the record where there were insufficient data to produce a reliable monthly hourly mean product.

Finally, as previously mentioned in section 3, there are insufficient observations owing to the persistently large SZA in the latitude bands from 55.5 to 59.5° S during May, June and July, and from

55.5 to 59.5° N during November, December and January each year. Therefore, data for these locations and times are excluded from the data record provided.

5. Considerations for Model-Observation Comparisons

The GERB flux products are TOA fluxes referenced at 20km. Several issues should be borne in mind when comparing to shortwave fluxes under conditions of low sun (high solar zenith angles). For twilight conditions, defined as solar zenith angles between 85 and 100°, GERB SW fluxes are based on a fixed twilight model derived from the CERES observations (Kato and Loeb, 2003). This model is designed to avoid biases in global annual mean observations and is not expected to provide good local or time resolved accuracy. In addition, despite being based on observed radiances, the GERB SW fluxes for solar zenith angles between 75° and 85° are expected to be more uncertain due to the limitations of the radiance to flux conversion and larger uncertainties in the scene identification.

The GERB instrument is geostationary and has a fixed viewing geometry. This means that angle specific biases in the radiance to flux conversion can manifest and will be scene, location and solar zenith angle dependent. In the shortwave the largest biases are seen over ocean when the glint angle is less than 20 degrees due to both the limitations in radiance to flux conversion and difficulties in reliable scene identification. The shortwave fluxes are also likely to have a larger error during significant aerosol events and over snow covered surfaces, as the radiance to flux treatment is not optimized for these cases. Finally, as a fixed land surface model is used in the radiance to flux conversion, seasonal variations in anisotropy for regions with significant changes in vegetation, such as the Sahel, are not captured.

These products, based on the GERB edition 1 dataset, have a scene independent correction for instrument SW aging applied as recommended in the data quality summary for the GERB products. This correction does not account for spectral variations in the aging which will manifest in variations to the rate of aging for different scenes. The average correction applied under-corrects the aging experienced for the bluest scenes such as clear ocean and over-corrects the aging experienced by the least blue scenes such as desert. The residual errors are most apparent towards the end of the record (see Parfitt *et al.*, 2016).

6. Instrument Overview

The GERB instruments are broadband radiometers making measurements of the TOA outgoing radiation from the Earth over the wavelength range from 0.32 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$. The instruments are mounted on the MSG satellites which are spin-stabilised and comprise of an optical and electronic unit. The optical unit contains the imaging optics and detector system, a despun mirror, quartz filter and two onboard calibration sources (visible and thermal). The electronics unit controls the optical unit and provides data handling. The detectors are arranged in a linear array of 256-pixels oriented north-south. The despun mirror is used to freeze the Earth view momentarily onto the detector array, adjusting the Earth's location by one pixel width for each rotation, enabling a full image to be built up over a period of approximately three minutes. The quartz filter is used to remove the infra-red component (4.0 μm to $>100 \mu\text{m}$) of the total incident radiation, thus providing a measure of only the shortwave (0.32 μm to 4.0 μm) component. The longwave component is derived by subtraction of the shortwave radiation component from the total radiation. The onboard calibration sources are used to

monitor the performance and maintain knowledge of the instrument's calibration. A detailed description of the GERB instrument is provided in Harries *et al.* (2005).

7. References

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8. Dataset and Document Revision History

Rev 0 – 12 May 2020

Rev 1 – 23 Oct 2023 Updated documentation to describe the new version 1.1 product.